

DIFFERENCES BETWEEN THE CONCEPTS OF TERM AND TERMINOLOGICAL LEXICON

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Annotatsiya: Hozirgi tilshunoslikda termin maxsus ilmiy- texnikaviy tushunchani ifodalovchi soʻz yoki soʻz birikmasi tarzida tavsiflanadi. Terminologik leksika oʻz tarkibiga mutaxassislikka oid noprofessional nutqiy kontekstda keng qoʻllanadigan soʻz va soʻz birikmalarini qamrab oladi. Mazkur maqolada termin va terminologik leksikaga oid ayrim mulohazalarni keltiramiz.

Kalit soʻzlar: termin, terminologiya, terminologik leksika

Abstract: The term is defined as a word or phrase expressing a special scientific and technical concept in current linguistics. The terminological lexicon includes words and phrases that are widely used in the context of non-professional speech related to the specialty. We present some comments on the term and terminological lexicon in this article.

Key words: term, terminology, terminological lexicon

Аннотация: Термин определяется как слово или словосочетание, выражающее специальное научно-техническое понятие в современном языкознании. В терминологическую лексику входят слова и словосочетания, широко употребляемые в контексте непрофессиональной речи, относящейся к специальности. В данной статье мы приводим некоторые комментарии к термину и терминологической лексике.

Ключевые слова: термин, терминология, терминологическая лексика.

It is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of term and terminological lexicon. The scope of use and distribution of terms is limited by a certain terminological system, and they act and occur in a specific way within the framework of human activity. The terminological lexicon includes words and phrases that are widely used in the context of non-professional speech, which has moved from the sphere of narrow specialization to the sphere of mass communication.

The term that has entered the sphere of universal language is separated from its terminology, terminological field and system, and is separated from the characteristics of the term.

The term was derived from the Greek word “terminus” which means limit, boundary. It is a word specific to science and technology, agriculture, art and culture.

The term is defined as a word or phrase expressing a special scientific and technical concept. The term has distinctive features:

- 1) the term is unambiguous or has an unambiguous tendency;
- 2) the term has a clear, nominative function and is not characterized by the functions of emotionality, expressiveness, modality. The term retains this feature both in context and out of context;
- 3) the meaning of the term is equal to the concept;
- 4) the term is stylistically neutral;
- 5) terminological lexicon is a separate system, etc.

According to A.S. Gerd (1991), a term is a natural and artificial language unit, that is, a word or a combination of words, with a special terminological meaning that clearly and fully reflects the main features of existing concepts at a certain stage of scientific development. Whewell (1967) defines terminology as a set of terms related to a specific science or a set of words used in the field of technology. By recording the meaning of terms, we also record the concepts they represent.

There are different views on the term. For example, for logicians, a term is a word that refers to a set of descriptions (or descriptions) of a specific object and is applied to it. Any word in any language can be a term. In science and technology, a term is an artificially invented or special word taken from natural language. The field of application of such words is specified or limited by representatives of one or another scientific school. Unlike universal terms, terms specific to science and technology are combined into terminological systems as hierarchical units, they achieve their meaning only within the same system, in which a logical (conceptual) terminological field corresponds to them.

According to Danilenko (1971), the perception of any process occurring in society is first expressed in terminology or occurs as a result of the transformational change of certain terms.

Lotte (1961) emphasized that the term should be viewed and treated as a member of a specific system, not as a separate sign. According to his opinion, the systematic relations in the content plan determine the systemic nature of the terms. The place and position of terms in the system of terms is determined by the place and position of a certain concept in the system of concepts.

In short, the terms embody a lexical layer that is fundamentally different from general literary words. Terminology is considered in the form of a set of special concepts, a set of special concepts combined into a system of terms, representing a categorical apparatus specific to different schools, scientific directions and specific ideas.

REFERENCES

1. Gerd, A.S. (1991). The meaning of the term and scientific knowledge//Scientific and technical information, Moscow.
2. Whewell W. (1967). The philosophy of the inductive sciences founded upon their history. Vo. I-II. – London.
3. Lotte D.S. (1994). Next tasks of technical terminology. Moscow.
4. Lotte D.S. (1961). Foundations of Constructing Scientific and Technical Terminology. Problems of Theory and Techniques, Moscow.
5. Danilenko V.P. (1977). Russian terminology. Moscow.